

DESIGNING FOR DIVERSITY: THE CHALLENGES OF LOCAL & GLOBAL SOCIAL SUSTAINABILITY

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Abstract

Principles and practices of social sustainability have rarely been included or actively pursued within conventional academic curricula. Indeed, a large number of academic institutions teaching architecture do not imbed environmental agendas as an ecological component of sustainability into the design culture they promote. It must, however, be noted that effective, environmentally responsible architectural design does not require striking labels such as “ecological design,” “green buildings,” or “sustainable architecture.” In fact, the frequency of use of these terms in a casual conscience sometimes increases the risk of eroding the impact of their intended meaning.

This paper focuses on a six-year process of injecting issues of social sustainability into an established academic curriculum at the University of Nicosia. The process engaged architecture students on platforms of both a social and an environmental sustainability and aimed at imparting technical skills, heightening ecological awareness and dissipating misconceptions regarding environmental sustainability. The process was in constant flux, susceptible to local and global socio-economic conditions and as such, the paper traces the process’ development of the initial placement and its subsequent adaptations and improvements. The paper examines and exhibits challenges, successes and lessons learned and will provide a guide and a roadmap to other, similar academic endeavours.

1 INTRODUCTION

To sustain is to survive, and to survive as a community requires that class and racial differences, as well as spatial and perceptual distances are overcome by good will and good design. As such, social sustainability combines design of the physical realm with design of the social world for creating successful places that promote well being by understanding what people need from the places they live and work. Accepting the reciprocal relationship between social process and the built environment means social relations are impacted by built form and, conversely, architecture is influenced by human dynamics. Thus, social sustainability is the condition whereby social process has stronger agency in affecting the built environment than the other way round.

Cultural heritage is civilization’s most valued asset, its identity through a proud sense of continuity as evidenced through time. Civilization and culture therein are imperative elements that buttress our identity as a community. Social sustainability aims to become a vehicle for people to live harmoniously and peacefully together and all citizens are to be treated equally and fairly in spite of age, race, colour and religion. From this perspective, social sustainability is neither local nor is it or global. Cypriot society, like other societies, is multicultural. Cyprus has a long history of migration and immigration; a fact that has

influenced city life in the past and present.

Nicosia, the capital of Cyprus, is estimated with 320,000 residents. Of those, about 50,000 live in the central part of the city, these being both immigrants and locals. Immigrants originate from the Middle East, Asia and former eastern-block countries. They are distributed throughout the central part of the city but they are more present within the Venetian walls of Nicosia, an area known as the Old Town. Immigrants socialise mainly with their co-nationals or other migrant's, limiting the relationship between Cypriots and foreigners. The Cypriots that come in contact with immigrants are predominantly employers. This hierarchical power does not easily allow other relationships to grow.

Acceptance of diverse groups of people is an important component for democratic societies to flourish, along with a strong surge of multicultural education where local colleges and universities promote an agenda of engaging students to dig deeply and investing in cultures other than their own. Basic principles for a multicultural education are the exchange of information and experiences, communication, elimination of racism, growth of sensitivity, solidarity, collaboration and general respect towards multicultural education.

2 IMPLEMENTING SOCIAL SUSTAINABILITY WITHIN THE ARCHITECTURAL CURRICULUM

Although sustainability is more of a constant inquiry rather than a definition, it is projected as the ability and the potential of all species and physical environments (manmade and natural) to survive. Sustainability's accountability to survival into the future is closely interlinked to diversity of species and functions in both animate and inanimate conditions. Non-anthropocentric environmental ethics imply a repositioning of design priorities that equate man to ecology and while some effort is spent in architectural academies to adequately understand the diversity of ecological systems in order to strategize in their favour, proportionally less effort is spent investigating notions of class, race and gender diversity and their role into the design process. Thus, the connection between social sustainability and a universal understanding of sustainable development is often lost within architectural education (Papadopoulou, et.al, 2014). Social sustainability in spatial terms is an admittedly difficult concept to articulate. However, if one accepts that the built environment has an equal and reciprocal relationship to social process, then social sustainability can be considered as the condition when this reciprocal relationship is no longer equal, but weighs more in favour of social process in the making of the built environment. In architectural education, concepts relating to diversity are commonly explored through an ecological lens.

The Architecture Department of University of Nicosia in 2009 introduced the Unit System (Each Unit has a distinct research question) and the Catalyst Workshops (honing on one particular and unique skill, not usually encountered in the curriculum). In 2015 the introduction of the MA in Architecture was introduced with a concentration in Sustainable Architecture. Studies focusing on sustainable design officially enter the curriculum for the first time in the 4th year with different concentrated courses (ARCH-441 History and Theory of Sustainable Design, ARCH-411 Sustainable Design).

Two of these unit studios, Sustainable Design Unit and Design for Diversity Unit, and one

of the workshops, *Building Blocks for Social Sustainability*, addressed the issue of social sustainability within a humanistic and cultural context, set on the platform of the built environment. It is the purpose of these studios/workshops to operate as a cross-disciplinary experience and to bring its participants in familiarity with other design specialisations such as sustainable urban design, landscape architecture, digital design, engineering and environmental and social science (Lapithis et.al, 2012).

The primary aim has been to introduce the knowledge and culture of sustainability to young architectural minds and to impart them with such skills that would enable them to bring forth a paradigm shift in professional arena. This has been achieved in the following two ways:

1. *Unit studios*: The process engaged architecture students on platforms of both a social and an environmental sustainability and aimed at imparting technical skills, heightening ecological awareness and dissipating misconceptions regarding environmental sustainability as the sole factor impacting energy management and quality of life. The process was one in constant flux, susceptible to local socio-economic conditions and as such, the paper traces the process' development of the initial placement and its subsequent adaptations and improvements. The presentation examines and exhibits challenges, successes and lessons learnt and will provide a guide and a roadmap to other, similar academic endeavours (Hekkers, 2012) (Lapithis, et.al, 2012) (Papadopoulou, et.al, 2015).
2. *Building Blocks for Social Sustainability - A Four-Day Design Workshop*: The workshop addresses the issue of social sustainability within a humanistic and cultural context, set on the platform of the built environment. Participants were called to consider matters of formal and informal urban structure, sense of community, social identity and ethics as those pertain to societal development in a diverse, multicultural setting. Operating under the premise that social sustainability can be attained through means of collaboration and common awareness, the workshop's findings aim to activate urban spaces in a three-dimensional and temporal manner in order to induce values of social and egalitarian participation (Postekkis, et.al., 2013) (Hekkers, 2013) (Lapithis. et.al 2013).

On a more tangible level, the mission of the specific studios and workshops mentioned above is to elevate architecture and design to a coexistence of a harmonious and productive synergy of man, nature and the spirit of place. At the end of the studio journey, the students should be in a position to face their architectural identity in such a way where sustainable design will not represent an attachment or a supplement to their design principles, but both entities operate as an integrated process.

At the start of the studio journey, a foundation needs to be set where all attempts to define sustainability are put on the table and theories are taken into consideration. The global, multifaceted nature of sustainability is presented in such a way that students become aware of its ever-elusive definition and the range of disciplines it involves. This realization is inevitably faced by the students with some trepidation, so time is set aside for individual consultations helping students identify their own niche within the network of possibilities of sustainable design.

Sustainability is expressed not only as a sound building technique but as a deep socio-

political issue that transcends generations, race and social class. The studio projects themselves, aim to explore the interdependency of issues of environmental, social and economic sustainability where students are prompted to develop individual, critical positions with regards to the broad concept of sustainability and to extend and explore those positions through their architectural design process.

3 RESEARCH QUESTION AND THEORETICAL PREMISE

Each student began his or her academic year with a particular research question that related their personal interests with the parameters of the studio thematic. Social and environmental sustainability were sometimes considered as tools to create good design and at times, they served as a pretext to improve existing conditions.

The research question can also be presented in the form of a thesis statement, or statement of intent. Previous research questions included:

- The Architecture of Reunification: the Case of Nicosia
- Traditional Cypriot Life: Slow or Fast?
- Interrelation of Slow Life through Renovation
- Bringing Nations Together Through Sustainability
- Slum Dwellings in Istanbul: Urban Retrofitting
- Negotiating Consumerism Ideology through Natural Environments in Urban Settings
- Incremental Revitalization of Abandoned Industrial Buildings
- Architecture as a Tool for Sustainable Reclamation: The case of Bangladesh
- Sustainable Urban Mobility: Multi-modal network planning – an alternative for Limassol
- ECONomic living: Re-defining our needs for shelter through Modularity and Sustainability
- BIY: Towards a Humanized Building Industry
- Affordable Housing and Urban Regeneration
- Mixed disabled and non disabled alternative education centre
- Time for Change: Quality of Life for the Homeless
- Sustainable Schools: from Concept to Reality
- Senior Living: Multigenerational Cohabitation Care Development
- Vulnerable Children: Implementation of Spatial Properties by Means of Imagination and Creativity
- Self-Sustained Mobile Living Communities on Water
- Working Within the Boundaries - The Verengaria Project
- A journey to Zakynthos- Integrated Design of the Seafront
- Green Economy and Sustainable Development: Bringing Back the Social Stability
- Food as an Instrument for Connecting Multicultural Communities
- Dealing with Stress in a Contemporary Urban Environment

A constant requisite of students from both the fourth- and the fifth-year studies throughout the five years of the studio's existence was the compilation of a thorough research of the theoretical premise behind their individually chosen research question. First order of business was to establish the research question (or thesis statement). Often students were comfortable in identifying their particular area of interest but had difficulties in drawing a succinct thesis statement that expressed their interest accurately and could clearly describe

their investigative intensions. To mitigate these difficulties, students followed a targeted lecture on how to hone in on a thesis topic and were encouraged to complete various relevant assignments in order to help determine their research question.

Once the research question was established, each student conducted his or her supporting research on relevant design principles, architectural theory and discourse, construction techniques, sociological and cultural processes, case studies etc. Students were encouraged to compose their research findings in the form of an academic research paper, including abstract, citations, bibliography etc. The students were expected to interpret and present their research in visual terms, in the form of diagrams, graphics, composite drawings, models and any other means that will enable the student to take the research finding and begin to understand it as a design tool. This proved to be a particularly challenging task, as students often found it easier to convey their research in words rather than images.

4 ASSIGNMENTS

Students attending studio in their fourth and fifth year share the same premises, studio times, instructors, lectures and workshops. The students from both years benefit greatly from each other's presence and momentum. Fourth-year studio students were encouraged to follow a schedule similar to the fifth-years, with a written thesis to support their chosen area of interest. Although this proved to be a good strategy to better prepare them for their fifth year, less time was spent on design work. In the years to follow, the Unit's studio will aim to offer more guidance on matters of allocation of time.

The fifth year is devoted entirely to the development of a major design project, self-initiated and based on a strong sense of professionalism and design maturity. Students of the fifth year are encouraged to take further their architectural, cultural and theoretical preoccupations and test their architectural imagination. Students are expected to use their so far obligatory experience of different design, constructional and structural models and their aesthetic properties to choose aptly and with sensibility from the full range of possibilities.

Individual guidance and recommendation of specific readings are given according to the students' chosen topic. Main concerns are research methods, study and analysis of design works and projects, appropriate presentation techniques, concept presentation, structural detailing and model making.

The two academic semesters of the studio were structured as follows: the first six weeks of the year were dedicated to researching the chosen area of investigation and compiling it in a graphical format. From then on students were required to develop their strategies, architectural proposals and master-plan (if relevant.) The second semester is then dedicated to developing a significant part of the architectural proposal to an appropriate level of detail, including plans, section, elevations, construction sketches and photo-realistic renders.

Key elements in producing a successful project were:

- Human and social impact of the built environment of the inhabitants of the project's particular environment.
- Dealing with complex environmental problems emphasizing the planning of large-scale buildings.
- Students are compelled to use their knowledge and experience of different

constructional and structural models, evaluate their aesthetic properties and choose aptly and with sensibility from a range of possible outcomes.

- Students are encouraged to consider how the luminous and acoustic aspects of design can be manipulated to facilitate the activities to be sheltered and explores how they can control objective mood and convey symbolic values.
- Contemporary perspectives on the relationship between human behaviour, designed environments and energy efficiency. In effect, the final project explores the implications of those relationships for the purpose and future direction of design education, design research and design practice.
- The link between quality of life and energy consumption, the variation in fossil fuel resources and end-use energy in Cyprus and International.
- The role of renewable energies in reducing environmental impact.
- social and an environmental sustainability and aimed at imparting technical skills, heightening ecological awareness and dissipating misconceptions regarding environmental sustainability
- local socio-economic conditions
- social sustainability within a humanistic and cultural context, set on the platform of the built environment.
- consider matters of formal and informal urban structure, sense of community, social identity and ethics as those pertain to societal development in a diverse, multicultural setting.
- Sustainability is expressed not only as a sound building technique but as a deep socio-political issue that transcends generations, race and social class.
- show the interdependency of issues of environmental, social and economic sustainability where students are prompted to develop individual, critical positions with regards to the broad concept of sustainability

5 LECTURES, GUESTS AND REVIEWS

Developing an understanding of design, maintenance and operation of the built environment while minimizing energy needs was a strong component of the studio's objectives. These issues were presented to students through a series of in-studio lectures by faculty members, expert guests and fellow students. Presentations were based on theory, case studies, technological advances and social issues. The basic framework of sustainable architecture, such as theory, ecology and technology was also offered to the students through the two supplementary courses they take as part of their fourth-year curriculum.

The studios fosters a culture of diversity of opinion and constructive criticism. Throughout the duration of the studio year, a series of guest lecturers and critics offered their time and advice to individual students, evaluating each project's merits, providing intriguing stimuli, feedback and helping each student elevate his or her work to the next level. All desk reviews with guest lecturers were conducted in the presence of at least one of the regular studio instructors to better communicating class objectives and to facilitate communication.

Guest critics have included practicing architects with a wide range of expertise, such as social sustainability, bioclimatics, urbanism and digital design, professors and instructors from local and international universities and artists specializing on ecosystems. Through their diverse educational background, the guest critics, having studied and worked in countries such as Germany, Spain, Holland, England, USA, UK and Greece, were in a position to offer unique pedagogical perspectives.

Most studio days began with a pinup of each student's work and his or her work is being discussed earnestly and constructively by fellow students and the instructors. As with all studios at University of Nicosia, there is a mid-semester review for all students where the entire faculty is invited as well as guest critics from other universities and professionals. These reviews prove to be an excellent means of coordinating progress in all same-year studios and they provide an opportunity for students to benefit from the experience of a large-scale presentation.

6 CONCLUSION

The studios primary aim was to introduce the knowledge and culture of social sustainability to young architectural minds and to impart them with such skills that would enable them to bring forth a paradigm shift in professional arena. Although the studio's priority was the promotion of sustainable principles, its thematic parameters underwent three basic transformations: its first field of investigation centred on combining conditions of Slow Life with sustainable design, its second was the exploration of the impact of sustainability on quality of life and the third focuses strongly on social sustainability. This transformation allowed the studio's activities to remain current and meaningful.

Also crucial to the studio's development was the transition from a specific site, common to all students, to the freedom of each student selecting their own site, based on their own interests and ambitions. The third transition was the movement from a structured assignment regime to a more flexible, but equally demanding schedule with far fewer structured exercise.

The students were not only able to produce mature projects touching on all basic issues proclaimed by the studio agenda, but most of them were able to greatly improve on their overall ability to solve complex architectural spaces and successfully present them in professional drawings and impressive computer renderings. This was partly the result of the instructors' perseverance and insistence that students should be handled as adults who are but a heartbeat away from professional employment.

References:

- Hekkers, M. (2012). Design a Sustainable Future. Cyprus Weekly newspaper. November 23
- Hekkers, M. (2013). Implementing Social Sustainability in the Walled City of Nicosia. Cyprus Weekly newspaper. April 19
- Lapithis P., Papadopoulou A. (2012) "Exploring Dimensions of Sustainable Design within the Architectural Curriculum", 18th Annual International Sustainable Development Research Conference Proceedings, 24-26 June, Hull, UK
- Lapithis P., Papadopoulou A. Postekkis, A. Tsaoushis, N. (2013) "Building Blocks for Social Sustainability: A Four-Day Design Workshop". ENHSA Environment Conference. Architectural Education and the Reality of the Ideal: Environmental design for Innovation in the post-crisis world", Napoli, 3-5 October.
- Lapithis, P. (2012) "Sustainable Design Education towards global energy management" Academia.edu. Sustainable Design Unit.

http://academia.edu/2097481/Sustainable_Design_Education_towards_global_energy_management

- Lapithis, P., Papadopoulou, A. (2010) “Exploring Dimensions of Slow Life filtering through Sustainable Architecture”. European Network of Heads of Schools of Architecture, European Association for Architectural Education. International Conference. Teaching a new Environmental Culture-The Environment as a Question of Architectural Education. Nicosia, Cyprus, 27-29 May
- Papadopoulou A., Lapithis P. (2011) “Exploring Dimensions of Slow Life”, International Solar Energy Society Conference Proceedings, 28August-2 September, Kassel, Germany. International Solar Energy Society
- Papadopoulou, A., Lapithis, P. (2014) “From Zero to Sustainability: Developing an Academic Culture in Sustainable Architecture “ Second International Conference on Architecture and Urban Design, Tirana, Albania, 8-10 May.
- Papadopoulou, A., Lapithis, P. (2015) ‘‘Historical and Sustainable Sensibilities: A Socio-Cultural Speculation within Architectural Education’’, International Conference on Sustainability in Architectural Cultural Heritage. Limassol, Cyprus. 11-12 December.
- Postekkis, A., Papadopoulou, A., Lapithis, P., Tsaousis, N. (2013) “Building Blocks for Social Sustainability: Nicosia within the walls” Cumulus Conference, National College of Art and Design, Dublin, Ireland, 7-9 November.
- Selected conference papers, student projects, research papers and teaching documents: <https://independent.academia.edu/SustainableDesignUnit>
- Selected design work, student life, photos, workshops and more info: <https://www.facebook.com/sustainable.design.unit>